

Applications of the (G'/G) -Expansion Method for Traveling Wave Solutions of the (2+1)-Dimensional Typical Breaking Soliton Equation and the Symmetrically Coupled KDV Equations

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Abstract

A variation of Expansion Method is proposed to seek exact travelling wave solutions of nonlinear partial differential equations. The method is implemented the (2+1)-dimensional typical breaking soliton equation, the symmetrically coupled KdV equations to illustrate the validity and advantages of the proposed method. As a result, many new and more general exact solutions have been obtained for the equations. This method can also be applied to other nonlinear evolution equation in mathematical physics.

Keywords: Nonlinear equations, -expansion method, travelling wave solutions, Riccati equation.

1. Introduction

Nonlinear phenomena can be seen in a broad variety of scientific applications such as plasma physics [1], chemical physics [2], fluid mechanics [3], solid state physics [4], optical fibers [5] etc. Thus finding of exact travelling wave solutions of those problems has a great interest.

Several powerful methods have been established and improved such as the inverse scattering transform method [6], the exp function method [7], the Backlund transform method [8, 9], the truncated Painleve expansion method [10, 11], the Hirota's bilinear operators [12], the Weierstrass elliptic function method [13], the Jacobi elliptic function method [14, 15], the tanh-function method [16]-[18], the homogeneous balance method [19], the sine-cosine method

[20], the rank analysis method [21], the ansatz method [22]-[24], the (G'/G) -Expansion Method [25].

Among these methods the expansion method has got much popularity due to its elementary idea, straight-forwardness and effectiveness. Bekir [26], and Zedan [27] applied the method on some nonlinear partial differential equations and obtained some new exact, travel-ling wave solutions. Zhang et al. [28] proposed the extension of the method to get more general travelling wave solutions. Zayed [29]-[30] proposed an alternative approach of the expansion method, namely changed the auxiliary equations, in which satisfies the Jacobi elliptic equation

$$[G'(\xi)]^2 = e_2 G^4(\xi) + e_1 G^2(\xi) + e_0,$$

e_2, e_1, e_0 are arbitrary constants, and the Riccati equa-

tion $G'(\xi) = A + BG^2(\xi)$, A, B are arbitrary constants. Guo and Zhou [31] presented the extended the expansion method, in which the solutions are presented in the form

$$u = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \{ a_i \left(\frac{G'}{G}\right)^{i-1} + b_i (G'/G)^{i-1} \sqrt{\sigma(1 + \left(\frac{1}{\mu}\right)(G'/G)^2)} \} .$$

Lu, Liu and Niuj [32] changed the auxiliary equation to

$$G'(\xi) = h_0 + h_1 G(\xi) + h_2 G^2(\xi) + h_3 G^3(\xi),$$

h_0, h_1, h_2, h_3 are arbitrary constants.

Ma [33] proposed the modified (G'/G)-expansion method and obtained new exact travelling wave solutions of the (2+1)-dimensional typical breaking soliton equation. Recently we have considered the symmetrically coupled KdV equations and have obtained [34] several new exact solutions using an extension of expansion method.

In the present letter, we shall propose a variation of the -expansion method which will play an important role to find exact travelling wave solutions of nonlinear partial differential equations. To show the reliability of the method, we applied it on some nonlinear partial differential equations, namely the (2+1)-dimensional typical breaking soliton equation, the symmetrically coupled KdV equations and find out their exact travelling wave solutions.

The rest of the paper was arranged as follows: In section 2, we have been describe the main idea of the variation of the (G'/G)-expansion method. In section 3, we applied the proposed method on the above mentioned two equations and obtained new exact travelling wave solutions. In section 4, conclusions were given, in section 5, references were given. Define all symbols used in the abstract.

2. Description of the variation of expansion method

In this section, we describe the main idea of the variation of the expansion method. Consider a nonlinear partial differential equation, say, in (n+1) independent variables

$$x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, \text{ and } t, \text{ as}$$

$$P(u, u_t, u_{x_1}, u_{x_2}, u_{tt}, u_{x_1 t}, u_{x_2 t}, u_{x_1 x_1}, u_{x_2 x_2}, \dots) = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Where $u = u(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$ is an unknown function, P is polynomial in

$u = u(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t)$ and its various partial derivatives, in which the highest order derivatives and nonlinear terms are involved. In the following steps, we present the main steps of the variation of the (G'/G)-expansion method.

Step 1. Consider the travelling wave trans-formation

$$u = u(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, t) = u(\xi), \quad \xi = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i x_i + Vt \quad (2.2)$$

Where $r_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ and V (speed of wave) are constants to be determined later.

The travelling wave variable u in (2.2) allows us to reduce the equation (2.1) to an ordinary differential equation for $u = u(\xi)$:

$$P(u, Vu', r_1 u', r_2 u', V^2 u', r_1 V u'', r_2 V u'', r_1^2 u'', r_2^2 u'', \dots) = 0 \quad (2.3)$$

Step 2. If possible integrate Eq. (2.3) term by term one or more times yields constant(s) of integration.

Step 3. Assume that the solution $u(\xi)$ of the Eq. (2.3) can be expressed as a polynomial in (G'/G) and (F'/F) as follows:

$$u(\xi) = \sum_{i=1}^m a_i \left(\frac{G'}{G}\right)^i + \sum_{i=1}^m b_i (G'/G)^{i-1} (F'/F) \quad (2.4)$$

Where $G = G(\xi)$ and $F = F(\xi)$ expresses the solution of the coupled Riccati equation,

$$G'(\xi) = -G(\xi).F(\xi) \quad (2.5)$$

$$F'(\xi) = 1 - F(\xi)^2 \quad (2.6)$$

Where prime denotes derivative with respect to ξ , $a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m)$, $b_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ are constants to be determined later.

These governing equations lead us two types of general solutions:

$$G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{sech}(\xi), F(\xi) = \tanh(\xi) \quad (2.7)$$

$$G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{csch}(\xi), F(\xi) = \operatorname{coth}(\xi) \quad (2.8).$$

Step 4. The positive integer can be determined by considering the homogeneous between the highest order derivatives and the nonlinear terms appearing in Eq. (2.3) as follows:

If $D[u(\xi)] = m$, then

$$D \left[u^r \left(\frac{d^q u}{d\xi^q} \right)^s \right] = mr + s(q + m), \text{ where } D \text{ denotes the}$$

degree of the expression.

Step 5. Substituting Eq.(2.4) into Eq.(2.3) and using Eq.(2.5) and Eq.(2.6), collecting all terms with the same order of (G'/G) or (F) together, left-hand side of Eq.(2.3) is converted into another polynomial in (G'/G) or (F) . Equating each coefficient of this polynomial to zero, yields a set of algebraic equations for $a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m), b_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m),$

$r_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ and V .

Step 6. Determining the constants $a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m), b_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m), r_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ and V by solving the algebraic equations in step 5. As the general solutions of Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.6) are already known to us, then substituting

$$a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m), b_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m),$$

$r_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n), V$ and the general solutions of Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.6), we obtain the travelling wave solutions of Eq. (2.1).

Finally we will consider a generalized version of the governing equations for G and F , which are as follows:

$$G'^2(\xi) = (1 - G^2(\xi)).(k'^2 + k^2 G^2(\xi)) \quad (2.9)$$

$$F'^2(\xi) = (1 - F^2(\xi)).(1 - k^2 F^2(\xi)) \quad (2.10)$$

Where k is known as the elliptic modulus and

$k' = \sqrt{1 - k^2}$ is known as the complementary elliptic modulus of the Jacobi elliptic functions [35].

The governing equations lead us to the following Jacobi elliptic expressions for G and F .

$$G(\xi) = \operatorname{cn}(\xi, k) \quad (2.11)$$

$$F(\xi) = \operatorname{sn}(\xi, k) \quad (2.12)$$

3. Applications of the method

3.1 Example 1: The (2+1)-Dimensional Typical Breaking Soliton Equation

In this subsection, we were studied the following the (2+1)-dimensional typical breaking soliton equation [36] in the following form:

$$u_{xt} - 4u_x u_{xy} - 2u_{xx} u_y + u_{xxx} y = 0, \quad (3.1.1)$$

Which was first introduced by Calogero and Degasperis [36]. Tian et al. [37] have reduced new families of soliton-like solutions via the generalized tanh method which are of important significance in explaining some physical phenomena. Mei and Zhang [38] have reduced more families of new exact solutions which contain soliton-like solutions and periodic solution based on a newly generally projective Riccati equation expansion method and its algorithm.

Let us now solve (3.1.1) by the proposed method. To this end, we see that the traveling wave variable

$$u(x, y, t) = u(\xi), \xi = x + y - Vt \quad (3.1.2)$$

Permits us to convert (3.1.1) into the following ODE:

$$-Vu'' - 6u'u'' + u^{(4)} = 0. \quad (3.1.3)$$

Integrating (3.1.3) with respect to ξ once yields

$$K - Vu' - 3(u')^2 + u''' = 0, \quad (3.1.4)$$

Where K is an integration constant.

Suppose that the solutions of the ODEs (3.1.4) can be expressed by polynomials in terms of (G'/G) and (F'/F) as follows:

$$u(\xi) = \sum_{i=0}^m a_i \left(\frac{G'}{G} \right)^i + \sum_{i=1}^m b_i (G'/G)^{i-1} (F'/F) \quad (3.1.5)$$

Where prime denotes derivative with respect to

$\xi, a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m), b_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ are constants to be determined later.

Considering the homogeneous balance between the highest order derivatives and the nonlinear terms in Eq. (3.1.4) we get $n = 1$. thus, we have

$$u(\xi) = a_0 + a_1 \left(\frac{G'}{G}\right) + b_1 \left(\frac{F'}{F}\right), \quad (3.1.6)$$

$$= a_0 - a_1 F + b_1 (F^{-1} - F), \quad (3.1.7)$$

Where a_0, a_1, b_1 all are arbitrary constants to be determined later.

Substituting Eqs.(3.1.7) into Eq. (3.1.4) and collecting all the terms with the same powers of F together and equating each coefficient to zero, yields a set of simultaneous algebraic equations for a_0, a_1, b_1 and K as follows:

$$F^0: K + Va_1 + 2a_1 + 6b_1^2 + 6a_1b_1 - 3a_1^2 = 0 \quad (3.1.8)$$

$$F^2: -Vb_1 - Va_1 + 6a_1b_1 + 6a_1^2 - 8a_1 - 8b_1 = 0 \quad (3.1.9)$$

$$F^4: -3a_1^2 + 6a_1 - 3b_1^2 - 6a_1b_1 + 6b_1 = 0 \quad (3.1.10)$$

$$F^{-2}: 8b_1 + Vb_1 - 6a_1b_1 = 0 \quad (3.1.11)$$

$$F^{-4}: -3b_1^2 - 6b_1 = 0 \quad (3.1.12)$$

Solving the set of algebraic equations for a_0, a_1, b_1, C and V by use of Maple, we get

Case 1:

$$K = 0, V = 4, a_0 = a_0, a_1 = 2, b_1 = -2 \quad (3.1.13)$$

Case 2:

$$K = 0, V = 16, a_0 = a_0, a_1 = 4, b_1 = -2 \quad (3.1.14)$$

Substituting the general solutions of Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.6) into Eq. (3.1.7), we get two types of travelling wave solutions of the (2+1)-dimensional typical breaking soliton equation, (3.1.1) corresponding to above mentioned two cases. Furthermore, based on the two types of general solution of the governing equations Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.6), there will be two different classes of solutions for each of two types.

Type 1:

Substituting Eq. (3.1.13) into Eq. (3.1.7) we have the solution of Eq. (3.1.1) as follows:

Class I: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{sech}(\xi), F(\xi) = \tanh(\xi)$

$$u_{11}(x, t) = a_0 - 2 \operatorname{coth}(x + y - 4t) \quad (3.1.15)$$

Class II: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{csch}(\xi), F(\xi) = \operatorname{coth}(\xi)$

$$u_{12}(x, t) = a_0 - 2 \tanh(x + y - 4t) \quad (3.1.16)$$

Type 2:

Substituting Eq. (3.1.14) into Eq. (3.1.7) we have the solution of Eq. (3.1.1) as follows:

Class I: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{sech}(\xi), F(\xi) = \tanh(\xi)$

$$u_{21}(x, t) = a_0 - 2 \tanh(x + y - 4t) - 2 \operatorname{coth}(x + y - 16t) \quad (3.1.17)$$

Class II: When

$G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{csch}(\xi), F(\xi) = \operatorname{coth}(\xi)$

$$u_{22}(x, t) = a_0 - 2 \operatorname{coth}(x + y - 4t) - 2 \tanh(x + y - 16t) \quad (3.1.18)$$

3.2 Example 2: The symmetrically coupled KdV equations

In this subsection, we have been consider the symmetrical-coupled KdV equations [39] in the forms:

$$u_t = u_{xxx} + v_{xxx} + 6uu_x + 4uv_x + 2u_xv = 0, \quad (3.2.1)$$

$$v_t = u_{xxx} + v_{xxx} + 6vv_x + 4vu_x + 2v_xu = 0. \quad (3.2.2)$$

The traveling wave variable below

$$u(x, t) = u(\xi), v(x, t) = v(\xi), \xi = k(x + \omega t),$$

Permits us converting Eqs. (3.2.1) and (3.2.2) into the following ODEs:

$$-\omega u' + k^2(u''' + v''') + 6uu' + 4uv' + 2u'v = 0, \quad (3.2.3)$$

$$-\omega v' + k^2(u''' + v''') + 6vv' + 4vu' + 2v'u = 0. \quad (3.2.4)$$

Where k and ω are the wave number and the wave speed, respectively.

Suppose that the solutions of the ODEs (3.2.3) and (3.2.4) can be expressed by polynomials in terms of (G'/G) and (F'/F) as follows:

$$u(\xi) = \sum_{i=0}^m a_i (G'/G)^i + \sum_{i=1}^m b_i (G'/G)^{i-1} (F'/F) \quad (3.2.5)$$

$$v(\xi) = \sum_{i=0}^n c_i (G'/G)^i + \sum_{i=1}^n d_i (G'/G)^{i-1} (F'/F) \quad (3.2.6)$$

Where prime denotes derivative with respect to ξ , $a_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m)$, $b_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$

, $c_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, n)$, $d_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ are constants to be determined later.

Considering the homogeneous balance between the highest order derivatives and the nonlinear terms in Eqs. (3.2.3) and (3.2.4), we get $m = n = 2$. thus, we have

$$u(\xi) = a_0 + a_1 (G'/G) + a_2 \left(\frac{G'}{G}\right)^2 + b_1 (F'/F) + b_2 (G'/G)(F'/F) \quad (3.2.7)$$

$$= a_0 - a_1 F + a_2 F^2 + b_1 (F^{-1} - F)$$

$$- b_2 (1 - F^2) \quad (3.2.8)$$

$$v(\xi) = c_0 + c_1 (G'/G) + c_2 \left(\frac{G'}{G}\right)^2 + d_1 (F'/F)$$

$$+ d_2 (G'/G)(F'/F) \quad (3.2.9)$$

$$= c_0 - c_1 F + c_2 F^2 + d_1 (F^{-1} - F)$$

$$- d_2 (1 - F^2) \quad (3.2.10)$$

Where $a_0, a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_0, c_1, c_2, d_1, d_2$ all are arbitrary constants to be determined later.

Substituting Eqs. (3.2.8), (3.2.10) into Eqs. (3.2.3), (3.2.4) and collecting all the terms with the same powers of F together and equating each coefficient to zero, yields a set of simultaneous algebraic equations for

$a_0, a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_0, c_1, c_2, d_1, d_2$ and k as follows:

$$F^5: -12a_2c_2 - 12b_2d_2 - 24k^2d_2 - 12b_2c_2$$

$$-12b_2^2 - 12a_2d_2 - 24b_2a_2 - 24k^2a_2$$

$$-24k^2c_2 - 24k^2b_2 - 12a_2^2 = 0 \quad (3.2.11)$$

$$F^4: 10b_1d_2 + 18a_1a_2 + 6k^2c_1 + 18a_2b_1$$

$$+ 6k^2b_1 + 8a_2d_1 + 10a_1d_2 + 10b_1c_2$$

$$+ 6k^2d_1 + 8b_2d_1 + 8a_2c_1 + 18b_2a_1$$

$$+ 18b_1b_2 + 10a_1c_2 + 8b_2c_1$$

$$+ 6k^2a_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.12)$$

$$F^3: -12b_1a_1 - 12a_0a_2 + 40k^2b_2 - 12a_0b_2$$

$$- 8a_0d_2 - 6a_1c_1 + 40k^2d_2 - 8a_0c_2$$

$$- 6a_1d_1 + 36b_2a_2 + 40k^2c_2 + 2\omega b_2$$

$$+ 40k^2a_2 + 12a_2c_2 + 20b_2c_2 + 24b_2d_2$$

$$- 4a_2c_0 + 16a_2d_2 - 4b_2c_0 - 6b_1c_1$$

$$- 6b_1d_1 + 2\omega a_2 - 6a_1^2 + 12a_2^2$$

$$- 6b_1^2 + 24b_2^2 = 0 \quad (3.2.13)$$

$$F^2: -24a_2b_1 - 30b_1b_2 - 24b_2a_1 - 8a_2c_1$$

$$- 8k^2b_1 + 6a_0b_1 + 6a_0a_1 + 2b_1c_0$$

$$- 16b_1c_2 - 8k^2d_1 - \omega b_1 - 8k^2a_1$$

$$- 18b_1d_2 - 10a_1c_2 - 12a_1d_2 + 4a_0c_1$$

$$- 12b_2c_1 - \omega a_1 + 2a_1c_0 - 18a_1a_2 - 12b_2d_1$$

$$- 8a_2d_1 - 8k^2c_1 + 4a_0d_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.14)$$

$$F^1: -2\omega a_2 + 12a_0b_2 + 8a_0d_2 - 16k^2b_2$$

$$- 8b_2c_2 + 4a_1d_1 - 2\omega b_2 - 4a_2d_2$$

$$+ 6b_1d_1 - 16k^2c_2 + 12a_0a_2 + 4a_2c_0$$

$$+ 6a_1^2 + 6a_1c_1 - 12b_2^2 + 8b_1c_1 + 12b_1a_1$$

$$- 16k^2a_2 - 12b_2a_2 + 4b_2c_0 - 12b_2d_2$$

$$-16k^2d_2 + 6b_1^2 + 8a_0c_2 = 0 \quad (3.2.15)$$

$$F^0: 4b_2c_1 - 2a_1c_0 + 2k^2a_1 + 6a_2b_1$$

$$-4a_0c_1 + 6b_1d_2 + 2a_1d_2 + 6b_2a_1 + 6b_1b_2$$

$$+2k^2c_1 + \omega a_1 - 6a_0a_1 + 6b_1c_2 = 0 \quad (3.2.16)$$

$$F^{-1}: -2b_1c_1 + b_1^2 + 2a_1d_1$$

$$+6b_1d_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.17)$$

$$F^{-2}: \omega b_1 + 8k^2b_1 + 4b_2d_1 + 6b_1b_2$$

$$+2b_1d_2 - 4a_0d_1 + 8k^2d_1 - 2b_1c_0$$

$$-6a_0b_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.18)$$

$$F^{-3}: -6b_1^2 - 6b_1d_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.19)$$

$$F^{-4}: -6k^2d_1 - 6k^2b_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.20)$$

$$F^5: -12b_2d_2 - 24k^2d_2 - 24k^2a_2 - 12a_2c_2$$

$$-24k^2c_2 - 24k^2b_2 - 24d_2c_2 - 12a_2d_2$$

$$-12d_2^2 - 12b_2c_2 - 12c_2^2 = 0 \quad (3.2.21)$$

$$F^4: 18d_1d_2 + 8b_1c_2 + 18c_1c_2 + 10b_2c_1$$

$$+10b_2d_1 + 18d_2c_1 + 6k^2c_1 + 6k^2d_1$$

$$+8a_1c_2 + 8b_1d_2 + 10a_2c_1 + 18c_2d_1 + 8a_1d_2$$

$$+10a_2d_1 + 6k^2b_1 + 6k^2a_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.22)$$

$$F^3: 2\omega c_2 + 2\omega d_2 - 12c_0d_2 - 12d_1c_1$$

$$+36d_2c_2 - 12c_0c_2 + 40k^2b_2 - 4a_0d_2$$

$$-6a_1c_1 + 40k^2d_2 - 4a_0c_2 - 6a_1d_1$$

$$+40k^2c_2 + 40k^2a_2 + 12a_2c_2 + 16b_2c_2$$

$$+24b_2d_2 - 8a_2c_0 + 20a_2d_2 - 8b_2c_0$$

$$-6b_1c_1 - 6b_1d_1 + 12c_2^2 - 6d_1^2$$

$$+24d_2^2 - 6c_1^2 = 0 \quad (3.2.23)$$

$$F^2: -12b_1d_2 - 18c_1c_2 - 30d_1d_2 + 2a_0c_1$$

$$+6c_0d_1 - 8k^2c_1 - \omega c_1 - 12b_2c_1 + 6c_0c_1$$

$$-8b_1c_2 + 4a_1c_0 - 8k^2b_1 - \omega d_1 - 10a_2c_1$$

$$-24c_2d_1 - 24d_2c_1 - 12a_1d_2 - 8k^2d_1$$

$$-16a_2d_1 - 18b_2d_1 + 2a_0d_1 + 4b_1c_0$$

$$-8k^2a_1 - 8a_1c_2 = 0 \quad (3.2.24)$$

$$F^1: 12d_1c_1 - 16k^2b_2 + 4a_0c_2 - 16k^2c_2$$

$$+6d_1^2 - 4b_2c_2 + 8b_2c_0 + 6b_1d_1 + 12c_0d_2$$

$$+4b_1c_1 - 12d_2^2 - 2\omega c_2 - 12d_2c_2$$

$$-16k^2a_2 + 8a_2c_0 + 4a_0d_2 - 8a_2d_2$$

$$-16k^2d_2 + 12c_0c_2 - 12b_2d_2 + 6a_1c_1$$

$$+8a_1d_1 - 2\omega d_2 + 6c_1^2 = 0 \quad (3.2.25)$$

$$F^0: -6c_0c_1 + 2k^2a_1 + \omega c_1 + 6a_2d_1$$

$$+6d_2c_1 + 6c_2d_1 + 2b_2c_1 + 6d_1d_2$$

$$+6b_2d_1 - 2a_0c_1 + 2k^2c_1 - 4a_1c_0$$

$$+4a_1d_2 = 0 \quad (3.2.26)$$

$$F^{-1}: 6b_1d_1 + 2b_1c_1 + 6d_1^2 - 2a_1d_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.27)$$

$$F^{-2}: 8k^2d_1 + 8k^2b_1 + \omega d_1 - 6c_0d_1$$

$$+2b_2d_1 + 6d_1d_2 + 4b_1d_2 - 2a_0d_1$$

$$-4b_1c_0 = 0 \quad (3.2.28)$$

$$F^{-3}: -6b_1d_1 - 6d_1^2 = 0 \quad (3.2.29)$$

$$F^{-4}: -6k^2d_1 - 6k^2b_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.30)$$

Solving the above algebraic equations for $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_0, c_1, c_2, d_1, d_2$ and k by use of Maple, we get

Case 1:

$$a_1 = 0, a_2 = -b_2, b_1 = 0,$$

$$c_1 = 0, c_2 = -d_2, d_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.31)$$

Where k, a_0, b_2, c_0, d_2 is arbitrary.

Case 2:

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{2}\omega + \frac{4}{3}k^2 + b_2, a_1 = 0,$$

$$a_2 = -b_2 - 2k^2, b_1 = 0,$$

$$c_0 = \frac{1}{2}\omega + d_2 + \frac{4}{3}k^2, c_1 = 0,$$

$$c_2 = -2k^2 - d_2, d_1 = 0 \quad (3.2.32)$$

Where k, b_2, d_2 is arbitrary.

Substituting the general solutions of Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.6) into Eqs. (3.2.8),(3.2.10) we get two types of travelling wave solutions of the symmetrically coupled KdV equations (3.2.1),(3.2.2) corresponding to above mentioned two cases. Furthermore, based on the two types of general solution of the governing equations Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.6), there will be two different classes of solutions for each of two types.

Type 1:

Substituting Eq. (3.2.31) into Eqs. (3.2.8),(3.2.10) we have the solutions of Eqs.(3.2.1),(3.2.2) as follows:

Class I: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{sech}(\xi)$, $F(\xi) = \tanh(\xi)$

$$u_{11} = a_0 - b_2 \quad (3.2.33)$$

$$v_{11} = c_0 - d_2 \quad (3.2.34)$$

Class II: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{csch}(\xi)$, $F(\xi) = \operatorname{coth}(\xi)$

$$u_{12} = a_0 - b_2 \quad (3.2.35)$$

$$v_{12} = c_0 - d_2 \quad (3.2.36)$$

Type 2:

Substituting Eq. (3.2.32) into Eqs. (3.2.8),(3.2.10) we have the solution of Eqs.(3.2.1),(3.2.2) as follows:

Class I: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{sech}(\xi)$, $F(\xi) = \tanh(\xi)$

$$u_{21} = \frac{1}{2}\omega + \frac{4}{3}k^2$$

$$-2k^2 \tanh^2(k(x + \omega t)) \quad (3.2.37)$$

$$v_{21} = \frac{1}{2}\omega + \frac{4}{3}k^2$$

$$-2k^2 \tanh^2(k(x + \omega t)) \quad (3.2.38)$$

Class II: When $G(\xi) = \pm \operatorname{csch}(\xi)$, $F(\xi) = \operatorname{coth}(\xi)$

$$u_{22} = \frac{1}{2}\omega + \frac{4}{3}k^2$$

$$-2k^2 \operatorname{coth}^2(k(x + \omega t)) \quad (3.2.39)$$

$$v_{22} = \frac{1}{2}\omega + \frac{4}{3}k^2$$

$$-2k^2 \operatorname{coth}^2(k(x + \omega t)) \quad (3.2.40)$$

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we have developed a variation of the (G'/G) -expansion method, in which we have used the full advantage of the well-known solution of the coupled Riccati equation. The presented method is used to find new exact travelling wave solutions of the (2+1)-dimensional typical breaking soliton equation, the symmetrically coupled KdV equation. The obtained results shows that the method is a powerful mathematical tool to solve a huge variety of nonlinear partial differential equations in mathematical physics. It is to be noticed that if we choose various type of auxiliary equations, we can obtain new types of exact travelling wave solutions, which can be seen in our further study. We shall also apply the generalization of the method on various nonlinear equations in our further study.

5. References

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